

SHOPPING BEHAVIOR OF WOMEN AND FACTOR INFLUENCING PURCHASE DECISION OF NON DURABLE GOODS

A. Venkeda Subramaniam* & Dr. P. Maruthu Pandian**

* Assistant Professor of Commerce, Nallamuthu Gounder Mahalingam College,
Pollachi, Tamilnadu

** Principal, Vidhyasagar College of Arts and Science, Udumalpet, Tamilnadu

Cite This Article: A. Venkeda Subramaniam & Dr. P. Maruthu Pandian, "Shopping Behavior of Women and Factor Influencing Purchase Decision of Non Durable Goods", International Journal of Interdisciplinary Research in Arts and Humanities, Volume 3, Issue 2, Page Number 58-61, 2018.

Abstract:

Today, women enjoy both personal and professional life. A women consumer manner is the study of how people buy, what they buy, when they buy and why they buy. Indian manufacturer plan the strategy to attract this segment, satisfy their needs and retain them. It also tries to assess influences on the consumer from groups such as family, friends, reference groups, and society in general. A study was carried out among 240 women consumers in Coimbatore district to assess their factor influencing in selecting the non durable goods. It was found that there exists a medium level influence among the women consumer. The variables area of residence, educational qualification, occupation, monthly income, monthly savings of the family and family type.

Key Words: Women, Buying Behavior, Purchase Decision, Non Durable Goods & Brand Awareness

Introduction:

Women enjoy both personal and professional life. Now-a-days women are not only playing role of hardcore 'house-wives', they are also playing a different role of 'chief purchasing officer' & controlling 85 % of all consumer purchases in the United States. She is the major factor in all purchase choice of her family. She has become family's purchasing representative. Indian manufacturers realized the need of her support and hence communicate with her and try to induce her through every possible media. They plan the marketing strategy to attract this segment, satisfy their needs and retain them. Women consumer behavior is the study of how people buy, what they buy, when they buy and why they buy. It attempts to understand the buyer's decision processes/buyer decision making process, both individually and in groups. It Studies characteristics of individual consumers such as demographics, psychographics, and behavioural variable in an attempt to understand people's wants. It also tries to assess influences on the consumer from groups such as family, friends, reference groups, and society in general. Retail sector is one of India's fastest growing sectors with a 5 percent compounded annual growth rate. Indian retail is expected to grow 25 per cent annually. But Behavior of consumer is a big field, and how women make purchasing decision should be the largest part of it.

Review of Literature:

Chrisy Dayamani (2011) suggested that factors like driving comfort, fuel economy and hospitality influence the consumers in buying car. Thus, the consumers buying behavior towards motorcycles is affected by host of variables.

Gonigal, George (2010) in their paper titled organized retail drives Gurgaon real estate mentioned that organized retail has been one of the key drivers of real estate development.

Kalyan Mukherjee (2015) observed that with increase of additional formal education amongst women, awareness level in regard to purchasing of non durable goods increases.

Vidya Panicker, Mohammad Khalil Ahmad (2015) in their paper titled a study on the general buying pattern of woman consumers in Mumbai, concluded that the woman possess a lot of dispensable income which they can spend freely on the products they consume themselves.

Statement of the Problem:

Non-durable goods like grocery, cosmetics are the basic products used by the consumers. They need these goods to satisfy their psychological needs. In the competitive era, the companies are trying to make their products more popular and thereby try to be successful. An understanding purchase behavior of women is an essential aspect as it reflects the influence of brands, buyer & customer type on the purchase of particular brands, etc. The success of the market or the failure depends on the purchase behavior of women consumers. Market focuses mainly on women consumers. Therefore, Marketers and manufacturers understand the interest and the needs of women to recognize them as a beneficial consumers segment and have started developing concept and to create products based on women centric. But, that is not being situation faced by women, especially in rural regions. So, even if the marketers and manufacturers recognize women as a beneficial consumer segment, the actual benefit did not reach the sector. This induce the question like what are the factors considered by women consumers while purchasing the non-durable goods.

Objectives of the Study:

The following are the objectives of the study:

- ✓ To study the Socio-Economic profile of the selected women consumers.
- ✓ To assess the shopping behavior of women.
- ✓ To identify the variables that influences the women consumers in selecting the non durable goods.
- ✓ To summarize the key findings an offer suggestion for the study.

Methodology:

Source of Data:

For the purpose of the study, the required data have been collected from both primary and secondary sources. Primary data from the women consumer have been collected with the help of interview schedule. Books, Journals, Periodical Broachers’, Research Papers etc form the sources of secondary data.

Area of Study:

The study was undertaken in Coimbatore District.

Sample Size:

To generalize the findings of the population as a whole. Two Forty women consumers (120 in each of the two non durable product categories) have been selected for the study.

Sampling Procedure:

For the purpose of the study the respondent were selected from different places of the Coimbatore district from different occupation, educational level, income and age groups. Convenience Sampling Methods was followed for collecting the response from the respondents.

Limitation of the Study:

The present study mainly relays on primary data. And hence, the data collected from the respondents may be biased in nature. The women consumer in Coimbatore District alone have been selected to express their opinion about the purchasing behavior of non-durable goods. And therefore, caution must be taken while generalizing the results of the study.

Findings of the Study:

Profile of the Women Consumer:

Table 1: Profile of the Women Consumer

S.No	Demographic Variable	No. of Women Consumers	%	
1.	Age (year)	Up to 20	62	26
		21-30	72	30
		31-40	50	21
		Above 40	56	23
2.	Educational Qualification	Up to 12	48	20
		Graduate	70	29
		Post Graduate	66	27.5
		Professional	56	23
3.	Occupation	Agriculture	36	15
		Employee	68	28
		Business	44	18
		Professional	76	32
		Student	16	7
4.	Monthly Income (Individual)	Below 10,000	10	4
		10001-20000	38	16
		20001-30000	82	34
		30001-45000	44	18
		Above 45000	66	27.5
4.	Monthly Savings (family)	Below 10,000	40	17
		10001-20000	32	13
		20001-30000	58	24
		30001-45000	88	37
		Above 45000	22	9
5.	Type of Family	Joint	124	52
		Nuclear	116	48
6.	Residential area	Rural	76	32
		Urban	92	38
		Semi Urban	72	30

Sources: Primary Data

From the table 1 it reveals that 30% of the women consumers belong to the age group of 21-30 years, 29% of the women consumers are graduates, 32% of women consumers are professionals, 34% of women

consumers monthly income is between 20001-30000, 37% of the women consumers family monthly savings was between 30001-45000, 52% of women consumers belong to joint family and most of the women consumers 38% are from urban area.

Brand Awareness on Non Durable Goods:

Table 2: Brand Awareness on Non Durable Goods

Brand Awareness on Non Durable Goods	Cosmetics		Grocery	
	No of Women Consumers	%	No of Women Consumers	%
Highly Awareness	68	57	61	51
Medium Awareness	40	33	45	37
Low Awareness	12	10	14	12
Total	120	100	120	100

Sources: Primary Data

From the table 2 it reveals that 57% of the women consumers are highly aware about cosmetic items and 51% of the women consumers are highly aware about grocery items.

Place of Purchase of Non Durable Goods:

Table 3: Place of Purchase of Non Durable Goods

Place of Purchase of Non Durable Goods	Cosmetics		Grocery	
	No of Women Consumers	%	No of Women Consumers	%
Retail shop	35	29	47	39
Department Store	71	59	43	36
Dealers	14	12	30	25
Total	120	100	120	100

Sources: Primary Data

From the table 3 it reveals that 59% of the women consumers buy the cosmetic items from departmental store where as the 39% of women consumers buy the grocery items from retail shop.

Factor Influencing in selecting the Non Durable Goods:

Table 4: Factor Influencing in Selecting the Non Durable Goods

Factor Influencing in Selecting the Non Durable Goods	Cosmetics		Grocery	
	No of Women Consumers	%	No of Women Consumers	%
Brand Image	18	15	12	10
Price	22	18	25	21
Quality	23	19	41	34
Advertising	16	13	15	13
Friends Opinion	11	9	9	8
Relatives Opinion	8	7	6	5
Spouse Opinion	10	8	4	3
Free Gifts	5	4	6	5
Discount	4	3	0	0
Joint Decision of Family	3	3	2	2
Total	120	100	120	100

Sources: Primary Data

Above Table notifies that the factor influencing the Non Durable Goods is selected for the study in case of cosmetics and grocery items. From the table 4 it is found that the majority of the women consumers influenced by the quality of the product in case of both cosmetics and grocery items.

Conclusion:

The current market situation is becoming highly competitive. The prominent gained by an consumer in marketing decision making compels the marketer to look at and sort out the mechanism of the promotion mix through the customers eyes. Hence, consumer behavior research has come into existent. In the present era women play a vital role in purchasing decision for non durable goods.

References:

1. Philip Kotler, "Marketing Management" 12th edition
2. Vidya Panicker, Mohammad Khalil Ahmad(2015)," A study on the general buying pattern of woman consumers in Mumbai" in NBR E-Journal volume 1, Issue 1 (Jan-Dec 2015)
3. Kalyan Mukherjee and Smitharai (2015),"A study on consumer awareness amongst women with regard to purchase of non durable goods in Guwahati city" in International journal of research and development in technology and management sciences-Kailash, volume 21, Issue 6, March 2015.

4. Lilly. J (2010),”A study on customer perception and preference towards branded products – with special reference to television sets”
5. K. Veerakumar (2016) article titled “A Research on Quality Factors Influencing Online Shopping” International Journal of Engineering Research and Modern Education, Vol-I, Issue-II, July – 2016. P.No.1-5.